

PHYSICO-CHEMICAL STUDIES OF COMPLEX FORMATION BETWEEN MOLYBDIC AND TARTARIC ACIDS. PART V. ELECTROMETRIC STUDIES

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When tartaric acid is added in increasing amounts to a definite quantity of a molybdic acid sol, the rate of change of specific conductivity per mole of H_2T i.e. $\frac{d\kappa}{d(H_2T)}$ (where κ is the observed increase in specific conductivity over the sum of the specific conductivities due to the components assuming no reaction), and the corresponding value of $\frac{d[H^+]}{d(H_2T)}$ reach maximum when the two components are present in equimolecular proportion, and this may be associated with the formation of a complex containing the two components in the same ratio as in the mixture i.e. 1 : 1. The observed increase of anionic conductivity of the mixtures as above over the sum of the components anionic conductivities, when present separately, is ascribed either to the dissolution of colloidal particles or miscelle ions initially present, or to the formation of a much stronger ionising complex imparting a higher concentration of the complex anions when present separately or more preferably to both of them.

Enhancement of electrolytic conductivity and H -ion concentration of a tartaric acid solution on addition of molybdic acid and the evidences associated with the formation of a complex in solution have been discussed.

When tartaric acid is added to a solution of molybdic acid or sodium molybdate, increased electrical conductivity and hydrogen-ion concentration have been observed besides enhanced optical rotations. Magnanini (1890) first observed such peculiarities with boric and tartaric acids and suggested the formation of a complex. Boeseken and collaborators (*Rec. trav. chim.*, 1921 40, 377) from numerous similar studies attempted to employ the phenomenon to reveal in organic molecules the co-existence of hydroxyl groups in certain proximity and the enhanced activity was ascribed to the existence in solution of an acid stronger than either of the components. Rimbach and Ley (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1922, 100, 393) electrometrically determined the H -ion concentration of mixtures of boric or molybdic acid with various hydroxyl containing substances and suggested for various mixtures some probable complex associations. Electrometric measurements have also been employed by Britton and Jackson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 1055) to investigate the possible complex formation between molybdic or tungstic acid and tartaric acid.

The enhanced conductivity and increased H -ion concentration cannot always be associated definitely with complex formation because examples are known where the electrolytic activity and solubility of a substance are found to increase in presence of a foreign substance. Boric acid is known to be definitely more soluble in solutions of tartaric acid, glycerine, mannitol, etc. (Burgess and Hunter, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 2838; Bancroft and David, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1930, 34, 897). Dumanskii and co-workers (*J. Russ. Phys. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 60, 229; *Kolloid Z.*, 1928, 44, 273) observed the peptisation of Sn and Ti hydroxides in tartaric acid solution. Lemcke (*J. Russ. Phys. Chem. Soc.*, 1905, 37, 1134; *Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1905, 52, 2179) observed that sodium or potassium chloride was more highly ionised in aqueous solution containing 9.87% glycerine. The activity coefficient of HCl is more in glycerol-water mixture than in pure aqueous solution (Lucasse, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*,

1926, 48, 526). Unfortunately we do not as yet know about the mechanism of the electrolytic dissociation to be able to ascribe to it or associate it with any particular property of the solvent, so that the hypothesis of higher dissociation of molybdic acid in tartaric acid solution may be verified.

Although the dissolution of colloidal particles has actually been observed, the idea of greater solubility alone cannot explain and correlate all the observed peculiarities without assuming a complex compound formation.

The object of the present investigation is to study the change in conductivity and H⁺-ion concentration in different mixtures of molybdic acid sol and tartaric acid and to associate the results with the indication of the formation of a complex in molecular ratio of the two components, and to examine whether any evidence of dissolution or breakdown of polymeric anions in molybdic acid sol into simpler ones, can be obtained from electrometric measurement.

EXPERIMENTAL

The methods of measuring the conductivity and hydrogen-ion concentration are the same as described before (Ghosh and Biswas, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 22, 279, 295). In Table I are represented the results of change of conductivity of a definite amount of MoO₃ sol, brought about by the addition of gradually increasing amount of *d*-tartaric acid. The corresponding *p*_H values of the mixtures are given in Table II.

TABLE I

[MoO₃] = Conc. of MoO₃ in the mixture = 253.7 × 10⁻⁴.

[H₂T] = Conc. of tartaric acid in the mixture.

κ_{MoO₃} = Sp. conductivity of MoO₃ sol when present separately at the same concentration as in the mixture.

κ_{H₂T} = Sp. conductivity of tartaric acid solution when present separately at the same concentration as in the mixture.

$\frac{d-\kappa}{d(H_2T)}$ = Rate of change of specific conductivity (diff.) per mole of H₂T of the mixture observed over the sum of the components assuming no reaction.

[H ₂ T].	κ _{H₂T} .	κ _{MoO₃} .	κ _{H₂T} .	κ _{Obs.}	Diff.	$\frac{d-\kappa}{d(H_2T)}$
69.43 × 10 ⁻⁴	7.60 × 10 ⁻⁴	20.38 × 10 ⁻⁴	27.98 × 10 ⁻⁴	33.03 × 10 ⁻⁴	5.05 × 10 ⁻⁴	790.2 × 10 ⁻⁴
126.6	11.84		32.32	44.54	12.22	994.5
190.3	15.54		34.92	58.47	21.55	1182.0
253.7	17.20		37.58	67.89	40.25	1586.0
507.5	24.60		44.98	108.60	58.82	1165.0
761.2	29.48		48.84	123.70	73.86	970.5
1015.0	35.40		55.78	135.5	79.72	785.6
1268.0	40.04		60.48	141.7	81.23	640.7
1522.0	43.35		63.73	145.9	82.17	539.9

TABLE II

p_H (MIX) - obs. p_H values of the mixture of MoO_3 sol and tartaric acid.

p_H (MoO_3) - obs. p_H values of MoO_3 sol when present separately at the same concentration as in the mixture = 2.618.

p_H (H_2T) - obs. p_H values of H_2T solution when present separately at the same conc. as in the mixture.

$\frac{d[H^+]}{d(H_2T)}$ - rate of change of $[H^+]$ (diff.) per mole of H_2T added, of the mixture observed over the sum of the components assuming no reaction.

p_H (H_2T)	p_H MIX.	$[H^+]_{MoO_3}$	$[H^+]_{H_2T}$	$[H^+]_{MoO_3}$	$[H^+]_{Obs.}$	Diff.	$\frac{d[H^+]}{d(H_2T)}$
			$[H^+]_{H_2T}$				
2.800	2.402	0.2410×10^{-4}	0.2189×10^{-3}	0.4598×10^{-3}	0.3983	-0.626	-1.001
2.480	2.164	..	.3238	.5646	0.6852	0.1208	0.9508
2.421	1.912	..	.3802	.8212	1.225	0.8028	3.173
2.370	1.790	..	.4268	.8676	1.622	0.4544	3.781
2.285	1.631	..	.6188	.7588	2.340	1.6702	3.283
2.208	1.485	..	.6177	.8687	3.428	2.5698	2.531
2.180	1.442	..	.6597	.9007	3.614	2.7138	2.188
2.150	1.428	..	.7023	.9433	3.724	2.709	1.838

DISCUSSION

We have already shown (Biswas, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1945, 22, 351) that tartaric and molybdic acids form a complex as follows :

It will be seen in Tables I and II that when we have started with two solutions at different concentration and adjusted the molecular ratio of the two in different mixtures, the value of $\frac{d[H^+]}{d(H_2T)}$ and $\frac{dx}{d(H_2T)}$ reach maximum when the two components are present in the equimolecular ratio. This maxima may be associated with the formation of a complex composed of solute molecules in the same ratios as that existing in the solution i. e. 1 : 1. The detailed systematic investigation in this connection is being dealt with in a subsequent paper.

Apart from ultramicroscopic observations, as was done previously (Biswas, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 23, 257) that tartaric acid causes dissolution of the colloidal particles or miscelle ions along with the formation of a complex in true solution can be shown thus :

Let us represent the complex formation in the ionic form as follows :

The anionic activity of the mixture of molybdic and tartaric acid solution should decrease considerably due to the formation of one slower moving complex anion at the expense of two faster moving anions. The anionic activity of the

complex solution or of its components, when present separately, can be determined by subtracting the conductivity contributed by the positive ions (i. e. H^+ ions) from the observed total conductivities. From some of the measured data, similar to those in Tables I and II, we have drawn up Table III below, where the calculated sum of the anionic specific conductivity of the two components assuming no reaction, are compared with the values actually observed in the mixture.

TABLE III

$\kappa_a(\text{MoO}_3)$ —obs anionic specific conductivity of MoO_3 sol when present separately.

$\kappa_a(\text{T})$ —obs. anionic specific conductivity of tartaric acid solution when present separately.

$\kappa_a(\text{obs.})$ —obs. anionic specific conductivity in a mixture of the above two.

$\kappa_a(\text{MoO}_3)$	$\kappa_a(\text{T})$	$\kappa_a(\text{MoO}_3) + \kappa_a(\text{T})$	$\kappa_a(\text{Obs.})$
0.57×10^{-4}	0.60×10^{-4}	1.17×10^{-4}	2.45×10^{-4}
2.76	..	3.36	7.30
12.26	..	12.86	15.94
13.86	..	14.46	17.26
12.02	0.14	12.16	19.16

Contrary to expectation it will be noticed that the observed anionic specific conductivities of the mixtures are appreciably more than the calculated sum assuming that there is no reaction. This phenomenon can be ascribed to either of the two following transformations or more preferably to both of them :

(1) The presence of tartaric acid may cause the dissolution of colloidal particles or miscelle ions when larger number of comparatively mobile small aggregates or simpler ions will be formed to increase the observed anionic conductivity in the mixtures.

(2) As we have assumed the formation of a stronger ionising complex than either of the components, and as the observed hydrogen-ion concentration in the mixture is more than the sum of the hydrogen-ion concentrations in their component solutions, correspondingly the concentration of the complex anion will also be more to cause the observed anionic conductivity to be more than the sum of the two components.

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